

MACHINE LEARNING-BASED PREDICTION OF SRG-CONFINED MASONRY COLUMN STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

In this study, machine learning (ML) models are used to determine the compressive strength of steel-reinforced grout (SRG)-confined masonry columns. Test results from the literature are used to train four ML models, namely k-nearest neighbor (KNN), linear regression (LR), gradient boosting (GB), and backpropagation neural network (BPNN). The ML models indicate high accuracy, with the GB model having the highest accuracy. The result of feature importance based on the GB model shows that the unconfined compressive strength, number of jacket layers, and column corner radius are the most important features. An equation for predicting SRG-confined masonry column strength is generated.

KEYWORDS

Column; compressive strength; confinement; machine learning (ML); masonry; steel-reinforced grout (SRG)

INTRODUCTION

Masonry structures are prone to damage due to overloads from changes in use, improper design and detailing, and poor performance under seismic loading. Thus, in recent decades, retrofitting of masonry structures has become crucial. Among various techniques available, externally bonded fiber-reinforced composites have been widely used as external reinforcement for strengthening existing structures due to their high strength and stiffness-to-weight ratio. While numerous works have studied the use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials, less focus has been given to fiber-reinforced cementitious matrix (FRCM) composite and steel-reinforced grout (SRG), despite their better vapor compatibility with masonry substrate. As such, there is a need to study the effectiveness of SRG to enhance the performance of existing masonry structures to facilitate the strengthening system design.

Recent studies have been conducted to explore the effectiveness of SRG jackets to confine masonry columns subjected to monotonic concentric compressive loads and to predict the corresponding strength increase. One-layer SRG-confined masonry prism columns with sharp corner conditions and one overlapping fiber face were studied by Santandrea et al. (2017). Results showed that the SRG jacket increased the average compressive strength of unconfined specimens by 33%. The effects of SRG matrix type, column corner condition, and steel cord sheet density were considered by Sneed et al. (2019) for masonry prisms confined with one-layer SRG jackets. In addition, models developed by Krevaikas and Triantafillou (2005), Di Ludovico et al. (2010), and CNR DT200 (CNR 2013) for FRP-confined masonry columns were evaluated to predict the compressive strength. The authors concluded that increasing the corner radius ratio ($\frac{2r_c}{b}$, where r_c is the radius, and b is the cross section width) from 0 to 0.31 increased the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry specimens by almost 10%. The confined compressive strength increased as the cord sheet density increased, but the increase was not proportional to the cord sheet density. Models by Di Ludovico et al. (2010) and CNR DT200 (CNR 2013) predicted the compressive strength increase of SRG-confined masonry columns within 9% and 5%, respectively. Ombres and Verre (2020) investigated the effect of number of jacket layers, overlap configuration of the fiber fabrics, and mortar type on SRG-confined masonry prism columns. Models by CNR DT215 (CNR 2018) and Cascardi et al. (2018) for FRCM-confined masonry columns were evaluated to predict the compressive strength. The authors concluded that the

Cascardi et al. (2018) model predicted the strength increase more accurately than the CNR DT215 (CNR 2018) model. The Cascardi et al. (2018) model predicted the strength of one-layer confined specimens fairly well, but the strength of multi-layer confinement was overestimated.

An experimental database of FRCM- and SRG-confined masonry columns was utilized by Thamboo (2021) to evaluate models by Krevaikas (2019), Cascardi et al. (2018), Balsamo et al. (2018), and CNR DT215 (CNR 2018) developed for FRCM-confined masonry columns. Results showed that the compressive strength of FRCM- and SRG-confined masonry columns was conservatively predicted by most models, and the model by CNR DT215 (CNR 2018) had good agreement with experimental results. Aiello et al. (2021) investigated the effect of number of jacket layers on SRG-confined masonry columns with rounded corners and one and a half overlapping fiber faces. The results showed that the strength of one-layer confined masonry columns increased only slightly, while multi-layer jackets produced a significant strength increase. Models reported in CNR DT215 (CNR 2018) and ACI 549-R13 (ACI 2013) guidelines for FRCM-confined masonry were utilized to predict the compressive strength. Results of the prediction models showed high variability, especially when the number of jacket layers was increased. The ACI 549-R13 (ACI 2013) model better predicted the experimental results of SRG-confined clay brick masonry columns.

Jemison-Parr et al. (2022) investigated the compressive strength of multi-layer SRG-confined masonry columns with different corner conditions, number of jacket layers, and number of overlapping faces. Results showed an increase in compressive strength with increasing number of jacket layers, although the increase was not proportional to the number of layers. The rounded column corners provided a slight increase. There was also an increase in compressive strength by increasing the number of overlapping faces. A database of SRG-confined masonry columns from past studies was reported by Al-Jaberi and Myers (2023). Models developed for FRCM confinement including those by ACI 549-R13 (ACI 2013), CNR DT215 (CNR 2018), and Balsamo et al. (2018) were used to predict the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns. The authors found that most models conservatively predicted the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns. The ACI 549-R13 (ACI 2013) model, on the other hand, was found to predict the compressive strength with reasonable accuracy.

In each of the aforementioned studies, methods for predicting the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns were based on those developed for FRP or FRCM confinement. Currently, no formula has been created specifically for SRG confinement of masonry. There is thus a need to determine whether a unique formula is required for SRG-confined masonry columns. To address this need, this paper presents a machine learning (ML) approach to predict the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns. A database is assembled consisting of test results from 102 SRG-confined masonry columns reported in the literature. The accuracy of four ML algorithms, namely k-nearest neighbor (KNN), linear regression (LR), gradient boosting (GB), and backpropagation neural network (BPNN), is compared. The GB model is used to develop feature importance (FI) and the Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) plot. A new formula to predict SRG-confined masonry column strength is generated using the GB model, considering the important parameters. The results are compared to the results of current equations for FRP and FRCM confinement proposed in the literature to be used for SRG.

DATABASE OF SRG TEST SPECIMENS

As discussed in the previous section, several authors have conducted experiments to investigate the compressive strength enhancement of SRG jackets applied to prismatic masonry columns subjected to monotonic concentric compressive loads. When a single test parameter was varied in the experiments, results showed that the compressive strength increase of SRG-confined masonry columns is affected by the compressive strength of the unconfined masonry column f_{mo} , matrix strength $f_{c,mat}$, equivalent fiber thickness t_f considering the fibers as uniformly distributed across the sheet width and fiber strength $f_{f,u}$, number of jacket layers n , number of overlapping faces n_{of} , column dimensions of width, depth, and length (b , h , and l , respectively), and corner condition r_c . Some of the effective

parameters are shown in Fig. 1. In this study, test data from 102 SRG-confined specimens reported by Santandrea et al. (2017), Sneed et al. (2019), Ombres & Verre (2020), Aiello et al. (2021), and Jemison-Parr et al. (2022) were assembled into a database for further examination. Material properties, geometric parameters, and test values of unconfined and confined compressive strengths, f_{mo} and f_{mc} , respectively, were included.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of: (a) unconfined masonry column, (b) SRG-confined masonry column

METHODS

Outlier Detection

The raw database (102 tests) was assessed to eliminate outlier data. This study employed the local outlier factor (LOF) algorithm, which is based on the KNN algorithm, to detect outlier data (Breunig et al. 2000). LOF is the anomaly score of each sample. The LOF approach extends the KNN approach (described in the subsection Machine Learning Algorithms below), which identifies outliers as the data point(s) with the greatest average distance to its k-nearest neighbors, by considering the local density of each point. This approach allows for more accurate identification of outliers in datasets with varying densities. The outlier factor considered in this study was 1.5. Four tests were detected as outliers, two of which had values of $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$ less than 1.0, and two of which had values that were significantly different than other replicate specimens within the same group.

Input Analysis

In this study, all parameters were considered separately as input once, and then once in combination as single variable that has a physical meaning of the ratio of the effective lateral confining pressure to unconfined compressive strength $\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}}$ with the same output, which is the ratio of confined to unconfined compressive strength $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$. $f_{l,eff}$ is the effective lateral confining pressure, which is calculated using Eq. 1:

$$f_{l,eff} = f_l k_H k_v \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where f_l is the confining pressure of the composite calculated using Eq. 2:

$$f_l = \left(\frac{b+h}{b \times h} \right) t_f f_r \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

In the Eq. 2, f_r is the effective stress in the fibers. In this study, f_r was taken as the steel cord ultimate strength except for the CNR DT200 (CNR 2013) model, in which f_r was determined using Eq. 3:

$$f_r = E_f \varepsilon_{f,d,rid} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where $\varepsilon_{f,d,rid}$ is the reduced circumferential strain in the fibers taken as 0.004.

The term k_H refers to the in-plane efficiency coefficient derived using Eq. 4:

$$k_H = 1 - \frac{b'^2 + h'^2}{3A_m} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where A_m is the cross-sectional area of the masonry column. $b' = b - 2r_c$, $h' = h - 2r_c$.

The term k_v refers to the vertical efficiency coefficient, which was assumed to be 1.0 for the specimens in this study, since the SRG jacket was continuous along the length for all test specimens considered.

Machine Learning Algorithms

In this study, the performance of four ML techniques, namely KNN, LR, GB, and BPNN, for predicting the SRG-confined compressive strength was analyzed. The algorithms are described briefly below. Further information is provided in the corresponding references.

k-nearest neighbor (KNN)

KNN takes the average (or another equivalent summary statistic) of the k-nearest data points for the target variable (i.e., the numerical value being predicted) (Altman 1992). When a new data point is entered into the algorithm, KNN uses a distance measure to identify the k training data points that are closest to it. The average (or another summary statistic) of the target variable among those k data points is then calculated and used as the predicted value for the new data point. The distance metric and the value of k are critical hyperparameters that can influence the performance of the KNN regression algorithm.

Linear regression (LR)

LR is a supervised learning algorithm used to predict a continuous output variable based on one or more input variables (Hastie et al. 2009). The algorithm models the relationship between the input variables (also called independent variables or features) and the output variable (also called dependent variable) using a linear function. The goal is to find the coefficients of this linear function that minimize the residual sum of squares between the predicted and actual values of the output variable in the training data.

Gradient boosting (GB)

GB is iteratively adding additional weak models to the ensemble (Natekin and Knoll 2013). Gradient boosting machine evaluates the error of the previously ensembled trees and seeks to recover it at each iteration while conducting prediction in the subsequent tree. As a result, the error continues to decrease in the subsequent tree ensemble.

Backpropagation neural network (BPNN)

The term "neural network" refers to a system of interconnected layers, including input, hidden, and output layers, whereby each connection typically has a different weight assigned to it (Han and Kamber, 2011). In general, the network output is optimized during the learning phase by changing the

connection weight. To reduce the mean square error between the actual and predicted outputs, a BPNN iteratively modifies the weights of the connections in the network. Since the weights are modified from the output layer to the backward direction, this approach is known as a back propagation neural network.

Performance metrics

Three common performance metrics were used to evaluate the ML models and equations, which are mean absolute error (MAE), root mean squared error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). MAE and RMSE are commonly used to calculate the difference between actual and predicted y values for n data points. MAE is a more robust metric than RMSE since it is not affected by outliers. RMSE, on the other hand, is a popular metric for regression problems since it penalizes large errors more severely than MAE. R^2 is a value between 0 and 1 that represents the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable(s). A value of 0 indicates that the independent variable(s) explain none of the variance in the dependent variable, while a value of 1 shows that the independent variable(s) fully explains the variance in the dependent variable. MAE, RMSE, and R^2 are defined in Eqs. 5-7:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i - \hat{y}_i \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where y_i is the actual value for observation i , \hat{y}_i is the predicted value for observation i , and \bar{y} is the mean of y value.

EXISTING PREDICTION EQUATIONS

Prediction equations

As discussed previously, researchers have proposed several equations to predict the increase in compressive strength of FRP- and FRCM-confined masonry columns as summarized in Table 1. However, there is no equation developed specifically for determining the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns. Therefore, the applicability of the equations mentioned in Table 1 for SRG-confined masonry columns was evaluated. The equations are written based on the general equation in Eq. 8.

Table 1: Existing equations to predict compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns

Reference	Equation	Confinement
(Krevaikas, 2019)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo}, \text{ if } \frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} < 0.09$ $f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[0.88 + 1.324 \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right) \right], \text{ if } \frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \geq 0.09$	
(Cascardi et al., 2018)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[1 + k \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right], \text{ where } k = 6\rho_{mat} \frac{f_{c,mat}}{f_{mo}}$	

(Balsamo et al., 2018)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[1 + k \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right) \right]$, where $k = \left(\frac{g_m}{1000} \right)^{0.662}$	FRCM
CNR DT215 (CNR 2018)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[1 + k \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]$, where $k = \left(\frac{g_m}{1000} \right)$	
ACI 549-R13 (ACI 2013)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[1 + 3.1 \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right) \right]$	
(Krevaikas & Triantafillou, 2005)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo}$, if $\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} < 0.24$ $f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[0.6 + 1.65 \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right) \right]$, if $\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \geq 0.24$	FRP
(Di Ludovico et al., 2010)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[1 + k \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right) \right]$, where $k = 1.53 \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right)^{-0.1}$	
CNR DT200 (CNR 2013)	$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[1 + k \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]$, where $k = \left(\frac{g_m}{1000} \right)$	

$$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[\alpha + k \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right)^\beta \right] \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Prediction Performance for All Inputs and One Combination Input

All tests in the entire reduced database (98 data points) were used for prediction performance. 80% of the tests were randomly selected as the training set, and the remaining 20% were used as the test set. The same training set and test set were used for all prediction models. The performance metrics of the trained ML models are shown in Table 2. The prediction results $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$ of the specimens in the reduced database for the same test set by four trained ML models are shown in Fig. 2. Considering test accuracy and all input features, the BPNN model has the highest accuracy with $R^2 = 0.913$, MAE = 0.072, and RMSE = 0.096. However, the BPNN model does not work well for combinations of variables as a single variable since it is a parametric model that is sensitive to the input variables. Among all models, the GB and KNN models work well by considering all variables and combinations of all variables as a single variable since these models are non-parametric models that can handle complex, nonlinear relationships between the input features and target variable. When a combination of variables is used as a single variable, these models can effectively capture the interaction effects between the input features and the target variable. The GB model has higher accuracy by considering all input variables ($R^2 = 0.910$, MAE = 0.079, RMSE = 0.098) and the combination of input variables as a single variable ($R^2 = 0.888$, MAE = 0.086, RMSE = 0.108).

Table 2: Performance metrics of the trained ML models

ML model	Set	All input variables			Single input variable		
		R ²	MAE	RMSE	R ²	MAE	RMSE
KNN	Training	0.887	0.076	0.112	0.824	0.082	0.135
	Test	0.878	0.091	0.114	0.792	0.107	0.148
LR	Training	0.645	0.145	0.192	0.261	0.178	0.277
	Test	0.560	0.164	0.215	0.177	0.191	0.295
GB	Training	0.889	0.079	0.107	0.908	0.070	0.098
	Test	0.910	0.079	0.098	0.888	0.086	0.108
BPNN	Training	0.909	0.073	0.097	0.261	0.178	0.277
	Test	0.913	0.072	0.096	0.183	0.188	0.294

Figure 2: Prediction performance of four ML models: (a) KNN model (all input variables), (b) KNN model (single input variable), (c) LR model (all input variables), (d) LR model (single input variable), (e) GB model (all input variables), (f) GB model (single input variable), (g) BPNN model (all input variables), (h) BPNN model (single input variable)

Comparison with Existing Equations

To compare with the existing equations, the complete reduced dataset (98 tests) was used instead of separating it into training and test sets. Table 3 presents the performance metrics of the four trained ML models, considering both individual input variables and their combinations as a single variable, along with all seven existing prediction equations. Based on the results, by considering all input variables, the four ML models have very high accuracy in terms of R^2 and a very low value in terms of MAE and RMSE compared to existing equations. However, the LR and BPNN models have very low accuracy by considering a single input variable since in comparison to the KNN and GB models, they are more sensitive to input variables. As a result, since one single variable is not representative of the features of all input variables, LR and BPNN models that are sensitive to input result in low accuracy.

Table 3: Performance metrics of the trained ML models and existing models

Model	R^2	MAE	RMSE
KNN (All input variables)	0.880	0.079	0.113
(Single input variable)	0.818	0.087	0.138
LR (All input variables)	0.649	0.144	0.191
(Single input variable)	0.074	0.210	0.311
GB (All input variables)	0.894	0.079	0.105
(Single input variable)	0.904	0.074	0.100
BPNN (All input variables)	0.913	0.070	0.095
(Single input variable)	0.146	0.222	0.298
(Krevaikas, 2019)	0.244	0.250	0.330
(Cascardi et al., 2018)	0.141	0.457	0.582
(Balsamo et al., 2018)	0.246	0.212	0.306
CNR DT215 (CNR 2018)	0.265	0.193	0.279
ACI 549-R13 (ACI 2013)	0.245	0.540	0.785
(Krevaikas & Triantafillou, 2005)	0.239	0.313	0.392
(Di Ludovico et al., 2010)	0.240	0.237	0.336

Importance of Parameters

FI and SHAP analyses were applied on the parameters affecting the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns using the GB model. Fig. 3 shows the analysis of the importance of the input parameters f_{mo} , $f_{c,mat}$, t_f , $f_{f,u}$, n , n_{of} , b , h , l , and r_c on the output. It can be seen that f_{mo} has the largest contribution (69.2%) to compressive strength. After that, the order contribution is n (14.7%), r_c (9.1%), and $f_{c,mat}$ (4%). All other parameters have very low contribution.

Based on SHAP value, specimens with a lower value of f_{mo} have a greater positive contribution impact on the value of $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$, while specimens with a higher value of f_{mo} have a greater negative contribution impact on the value of $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$. Specimens with a higher n have a greater positive contribution impact on the value of $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$, while specimens with a lower n have a greater negative contribution impact on the value of $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$. In fact, specimens with a large n have high compressive strength, while those with a small n have a low compressive strength. This pattern is also true for r_c , but its effect on the result in both positive and negative terms is less than that of n . These findings are consistent with those by Jemison-Parr et al. (2022), who observed a nonlinear increase in compressive strength with increasing number of jacket layers, and that rounded column corners provided only a slight increase in the confined compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns.

Figure 3: FI and SHAP value of input parameters

FORMULATION OF EQUATION

The aforementioned analyses indicated that the ML models considered herein were able to predict the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns. In order to simplify the design of SRG-confined masonry columns, an explicit equation based on the ML model was developed. The general Eq. 8 was chosen to consider the effect of SRG confinement. The trained GB model was used to determine value of the coefficients α , k , and β to best predict the compressive strength of a SRG-confined masonry column. $\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}}$ was continuously varied from minimum to maximum of its value in the database. The curve fitted to the predicted results of $\frac{f_{mc}}{f_{mo}}$ versus $\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}}$ yields Eq. 9:

$$f_{mc} = f_{mo} \left[1.49 + 0.84 \left(\frac{f_{l,eff}}{f_{mo}} \right)^{2.9} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

The fitting curve has $R^2 = 0.270$, $MAE = 0.265$, and $RMSE = 0.319$. The result shows that although the GB model has high accuracy, the fitting curve cannot predict the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns very well. The proposed equation is slightly more accurate than most of the existing prediction equations in Table 3. This result suggests that the general formula of Eq. 8 may not accurately reflect the interaction of all effective parameters for SRG-confined masonry.

CONCLUSION

This study presented an equation to predict the compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns based on the GB-trained ML model and a general equation. A database comprising experimental data from 102 SRG-confined masonry columns was established. The performance of trained ML models by considering all input variables and combinations of input variables as a single variable was compared to existing prediction equations. A new equation based on the GB ML model by considering a combination of input variables as a single variable was generated to predict the compressive strength of a confined masonry column. The findings of this study lead to the following conclusions:

1. Seven equations for prediction of compressive strength in FRCM- and FRP-confined columns proposed by previous researchers were evaluated using the SRG database. These equations showed low accuracy, with R^2 values ranging from 0.141 to 0.245 for predicting an increase in compressive strength provided by SRG jackets.
2. Four ML algorithms used to predict the increase in compressive strength increased the accuracy of the prediction up to 0.913 in R^2 . All four models work well and have high accuracy when

considering all input variables. Among them, the KNN and GB models had high accuracy by considering all input variables and combinations of them as a single variable. The GB model with high accuracy (about 0.894 and 0.904 in R^2 by considering all input variables and combinations of them as a single variable, respectively) was chosen for FI, SHAP value analyses, and the proposed equation.

3. To address the issue of black-box problem associated with ML models, FI, SHAP values for all effective parameters, and prediction equations based on the GB model and general equation by considering the SRG database for increasing compressive strength were developed. FI and SHAP value showed that the number of jacket layers and column corner radius are the important factors, following the column unconfined compressive strength. Although the GB model, by considering combinations of input variables as a single variable, has high accuracy, fitting just one curve based on the general equation was not able to predict the increase in compressive strength of a confined masonry column with high accuracy.

The current research proposes that ML models can predict the increase in compressive strength of SRG-confined masonry columns with high accuracy. However, there is a negligible increase in the accuracy of the proposed equation compared to previous equations. There is a need for more research to improve the fitting curve for the GB model.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.